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nIoVe

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Deliverable

DELIVERABLE D8.3 nIoVe's web site

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Executive Summary

The present document is a deliverable of the nloVe project as part of Work Package 8: Dissemination, Exploitation & Standardization, Task 8.1 Communication & Dissemination Activities. The purpose of the deliverable is to provide an overview of the project's website, its design and functionalities along with its updates throughout the project implementation.

The website was designed and developed by SEEMS with the support of all members of the Consortium. The website was designed in such a way as to ensure maximum usability, accessibility and consistency. The main goal is the constant update of all identified target groups regarding the project's results and achievements.

The website's content will be regularly updated with news, events, publications, press releases, public deliverables, links to social media and other dissemination materials (e.g. multimedia) to achieve greater impact. The website's software will be also regularly updated to ensure effective maintenance and information security.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The purpose of Deliverable D8.3 – “nloVe’s web site” is to present the structure and functionalities of the project’s website, the tools used for its development but also the tools that will be used for its assessment.

The website was developed in a way to ensure maximum usability, accessibility and consistency. The website is ultimately linked with all dissemination and communication activities of the project. The main goal is the constant update of all identified target groups regarding the project’s results and achievements to achieve maximum impact.

The objectives of the project’s web site include the following:

- To support any dissemination activity.
- To enable smooth communication and knowledge among stakeholders.
- To include content (e.g. dissemination material and achievements) relevant to all target groups.
- To be user-friendly and compatible.
- To be accessible by all types of users.
- To ensure its use even after the project ends.

1.2 Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

Deliverable D8.3 is the third deliverable of WP8 – “Dissemination, Exploitation & Standardization”. The present deliverable is related with the following Deliverables of the nloVe project as listed below.

Table 1: Relation to Other Tasks

Deliverable	Title	Lead beneficiary	Dissemination level
D8.1	Detailed dissemination and communication plan (M9)	SEEMS	PU
D8.1	Detailed dissemination and communication plan (M18)	SEEMS	PU
D8.1	Detailed dissemination and communication plan (M27)	SEEMS	PU
D8.1	Detailed dissemination and communication plan (M36)	SEEMS	PU
D8.2	Report on Dissemination Activities, Public Participation and Awareness (M36)	SEEMS	PU

- i) contact information
- j) European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme acknowledgment.

The website includes the project description, prospects, news & events related to the nloVe topics and announcements. The project web site also includes a usable content management system, where partners can put articles about intermediate project results. Furthermore, it will contain public documents (i.e. project publications) available for download and links to other relevant sites such as nloVe partners relevant projects, relevant EC sites, cyber-security platforms etc.

The website allows on-line collaboration between partners that includes exchange of documents and support for discussion lists and a calendar with information about forthcoming events and tasks (workshops, meetings, and deadlines). All the intermediate results of the project (internal management/progress reports, deliverables, presentations, papers, data sets, software, etc.) will be available to the partners through this website.

The hosting, maintenance and update of the website is SEEMS responsibility. All partners will be responsible to enrich the website's content with relevant dissemination material (e.g. news, publications, deliverables, multimedia etc).

2.2 Development Approach

nloVe's website design responds to the user's behavior and environment based on screen size, platform and orientation. The website includes the following features:

- **Flexible layout** - Flexible grid to create the website layout that will dynamically resize to any width.
- **Media queries** - An extension to media types when targeting and including styles.
- **Flexible multimedia** – Scalable media (images, video and other), by adapting the size of the media as the size of the viewport changes.

Figure 2: Desktop and mobile view of the Website

The website uses content blocks, so that the content (text, video, gallery, HTML code etc):

- Change position within the website
- Be activated or deactivated any time
- Have its prominence increased or decreased

2.3 Site structure at launch

The web site was launched during the very first month of the project, therefore at this stage it lacks publications and public deliverables, as well as different dissemination material and multimedia content. Nevertheless, the website includes today, all basic information for a H2020 Research and Innovation project.

All sections of the website have on top the project’s logo and at the bottom of each page reference to Horizon 2020 and European Commission (EC) support.

Home: The Home page is designed to attract the attention of the visitor.

Figure 3: Website Home Page

Project: The Project tab includes an overview of the project, its objectives and architecture.

nIoVe aims to deploy a novel multi-layered interoperable cybersecurity solution for the Internet-of-Vehicles (IoV), with emphasis of the Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) ecosystem by employing an advanced cybersecurity system enabling all relevant stakeholders and incident response teams to share cyber threat intelligence, synchronize and coordinate their cybersecurity strategies, response and recovery activities. To do so the project develops a set of in-vehicle and V2X data collectors that will feed nIoVe's machine learning platform and tools for threat analysis and situational awareness across the IoV ecosystem. Advanced visual and data analytics are further enhanced and adapted to boost cyber-threat detection performance under complex attack scenarios, while IoV stakeholders are jointly engaged in incident response activities through trusted mechanisms. The proposed approach is supported by interoperable data exchange between existing and newly proposed cybersecurity tools. nIoVe solution will be demonstrated and validated in 3 pilots: Hybrid execution environment, simulated environment and real-world conditions.

Figure 4: The 'Project' Section of the Website

Dissemination: The Dissemination tab includes research papers, talks, public deliverables, and other dissemination materials provided by the consortium members.

Outreach: The Outreach tab includes conferences, press releases and workshops organized during the project.

Partners: The Partners tab provides a presentation of all partners taking part in the project with their logos and a link to their websites.

Figure 5: The 'Partners' Section of the Website

Organization: The Organization tab includes three sub-sections: a) Organizational structure, b) Work Packages and c) Deliverables.

Figure 6: The 'Organization' Section of the Website

Contact: The Contact tab leads visitors to the project coordinator.

Figure 7: The 'Contact' Section of the Website

Private area: An area accessible only by consortium partners allows on-line collaboration within the consortium. Every user must register in order to obtain a username and password. The objective is to have a secure and private place to exchange information and documents between partners. It will also be used as a repository of deliverables, meeting minutes and all documents relevant to the project.

Figure 8: The login panel to access the private area

2.4 Site amendments at Month 6

The website's main structure remains the same, but the following modifications were made.

Social Media: One powerful tool to enhance the project's communication strategy is to establish its presence in social media networks. A Twitter and a LinkedIn account have been created presenting all actions and events during the implementation of the project. Also, a Facebook Page has been set up. This page includes posts, shares, videos and every other element related to the communication strategy of the project. This effort will be reinforced by the existing accounts that are already used by the participants of the consortium.

The links of the Social Media accounts for the nIoVe project are the following:

- Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/NioveProject>
- Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/NioveProject/>
- LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nioveproject/>

Figure 9: Facebook Account

Figure 10: Twitter Account

Figure 11: LinkedIn Account

Home: A Latest News section is added in the home page. Recent tweets are also displayed next to the Latest News. This section of the website is used to present news about the actions of all members of the consortium during the implementation of the project.

Figure 12: Latest News and Recent Tweets

Footer: Links to the official social media accounts of nIoVe have been added to the footer of the website.

Figure 13: The 'Footer' Section updated

Project: Related European Projects were added.

Figure 14: The ‘Project’ Section updated

Dissemination: Talks and Publications were added.

Figure 15: The ‘Dissemination’ Section updated

Contact: In the Contact area a contact form is added along with the coordinator’s contact details.

Figure 16: The ‘Contact’ Section updated

Private area: The private area consists of a repository, a calendar and an event list. Partners can upload a document (deliverable, minutes of meetings or dissemination materials) or submit an event.

Figure 17: The 'Private Area' Section updated

2.5 Technologies Used

The website is built using the Joomla Content Management System (CMS) which provides an easy interface to manage content and complete regular updates. The website is based on a flexible and responsive framework that guarantees an adjusted vision depending on the device used (e.g. PC, laptop, smartphone, tablet).

The website uses Joomla extensions to expand its functionalities including multimedia, news display, design and communication. Joomla core is running on PHP and on a database layer for data storage that supports MySQL.

The website implements the SSL Certificate DV (domain validated). The SSL certificate (Secure Sockets Layer) is a protocol (https) designed to allow applications to transmit information securely. The private area is password protected. Every user is allowed for registration in order to obtain login and password.

In order to separate the content from presentation (layout, colors and fonts) the website uses a very well-known style sheet language Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). With this separation content accessibility, flexibility and control is enhanced while complexity and repetition in the structural content is reduced.

2.6 Impact Assessment

The website's impact will be assessed via Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). KPIs will be determined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Google analytics will be used to analyze the KPIs and adjust the website accordingly. Google Analytics is one of the leading and most powerful tools for monitoring and analyzing "traffic" on a Website. It provides a huge amount of information about who visited the website, what the visitors searched for and how they arrived on the website. The usefulness of Google Analytics is very important. Thanks to this tool the consortium will have a full insight on the traffic of nloVe's website. It is also possible for Google Analytics to provide statistics about the rate of visitors' return to the website and the duration of their visit as well as information

about the browser from which the visitors visited the website and the ways they found the website (keywords, referral links etc).

Some indicative KPIs that will be used for the website’s assessment are displayed below:

- Unique visitors
- Repeated visitors
- Duration of each visit
- Number of viewed pages per visit
- Popular site content

Figure 18: Google Analytics Dashboard View

Figure 19: LinkedIn Analytics View

Figure 20: Twitter Analytics View

Figure 21: Facebook Analytics View

Website and social media analytics are examined once a month. The purpose of this, is to continually improve the way the project is disseminated in accordance with the communication strategy. Below, some indicative statistics are presented from nIoVe’s presence on social media.

Facebook	Total Page Likes	Total Page Followers		
	37	40		
LinkedIn	Total Page Followers	Viewed Profile	Post Views	Search Appearances
	37	40	275	2
Twitter	Total Page Followers	Viewed Profile	Post Views	
	27	2100	163	

Table 2: Social Media Analytics M1-M6.

2.7 Future modifications

The website will be constantly adapted throughout the whole duration of the project. A list of future modifications is displayed below:

- Multimedia enrichment (photos, videos etc) will be added.
- Banners for public and stakeholder participation in the project's events and activities will be published such as workshops, conferences and other activities.

3. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the updated version of nloVe’s website which is the basic tool to communicate and disseminate the project’s results and activities. The main purpose is to raise awareness about the project results and achievements and to enhance collaboration between the consortium partners. The website provides general public information about the project, dissemination material and activities. It is also a repository for deliverables and a working area for the partners to exchange information.

The website is designed to attract the identified target groups and ensure nloVe’s visibility to all stakeholders and general public. The website’s content will be constantly updated by SEEMS with the contribution of all consortium partners. The website will be maintained and adjusted based on regular assessment to achieve greater impact.

nloVe’s website will be constantly adjusted to the overall strategy that will be derived from the deliverable “D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan”.

References

- [1] Forrest Stroud, responsive website design - RWD, [Online].
<https://www.webopedia.com/TERM/R/responsive-website.html>
- [2] Joomla CMS, [Online]. Available: <https://www.joomla.org/>.
- [4] Google Analytics, [Online]. Available:
<https://marketingplatform.google.com/about/analytics/>